

Feasibility Test for Determination of Dosimeter Response for the Watts Bar Unit 1 Reactor Extended Belt-line Region Using the DRF Method

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ABSTRACT

New methods for solving 3-D reactor pressure vessel (RPV) dosimetry problems are emerging as the operating lifetimes of nuclear power reactors continue to increase. Accurately quantifying neutron fluence and its associated damage in RPV regions beyond the traditional beltline has become increasingly important. This work applies the detector response function (DRF) methodology to a 3-D RPV dosimetry problem using the TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Benchmark as the reference model. A test problem consisting of four axial fuel segments is used to evaluate the effectiveness of the DRF approach for pressure vessel fluence calculations. DRF predictions are compared against reference MCNP Monte Carlo results. The good agreement between the two methods demonstrates the soundness of the DRF approach; however, additional analysis and optimization are required before extending the method to a full-core DRF solution.

Keywords: Reactor Pressure Vessel Fluence, Neutronics, CADIS

1. INTRODUCTION

Interest in accurate and fast 3-D dosimetry response calculations for reactor pressure vessels (RPV) is increasing as U.S. nuclear power reactors continue operating beyond their original design lifetimes. For standard operating lifespans, the traditional 2-D synthesis deterministic approach, focused primarily on the beltline region, has been sufficient. However, life-extension initiatives raise concerns that structures outside the beltline region may have accumulated significant neutron fluence damage that must be evaluated. Assessing these out-of-beltline regions requires full 3-D particle transport calculations, which are considerably more computationally demanding than the previously used 2-D synthesis methods. This paper investigates the application of the hybrid detector response function (DRF) methodology [1] to perform reactor dosimetry using a full 3-D transport calculation of the TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 Benchmark model.

The DRF method is considered a hybrid approach because it uses an approximate importance function, computed with a deterministic solver, to accelerate a series of fixed-source Monte Carlo simulations using CADIS [2] to obtain the DRF coefficients. These coefficients are then coupled with the core fission neutron source to calculate the dosimetry response. This method enables quick, detailed uncertainty quantification by precomputing DRF coefficients as functions of various reactor parameters.

2. THEORY

The DRF method is based on the MRT methodology [3], and it determines the response of a detector or dosimeter. The source phase-space of a system that includes a detector or dosimeter is divided into sub-regions and a corresponding coefficient for each sub-region is found. The DRF coefficients represent the average contribution a particle from one sub-region makes to the overall response. A database of DRF coefficients is created through pre-calculations that use Monte Carlo fixed-source simulations to find the partial contributions [1]. A simple algebraic calculation of the response is achieved by coupling the DRF coefficients with a known source.

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3. METHODOLOGY

The DRF method is applied to a test problem based on the benchmark model of the TVA Watts Bar Unit 1 reactor [4] [5]. The method uses PENTRAN as a deterministic solver [6] for an approximate importance function and MCNP as a Monte Carlo code [7] for performing fixed-source calculations to obtain DRF coefficients. This study considers only a small axial portion of one fuel rod, called the limited test region (LTR) as a neutron source for the test problem. Additionally, only the 7 highest energy groups (in a range of 6.0 MeV - 17.3 MeV) of the 47 energy groups, from the BUGLE-B7 library [8], are simulated. The computation time of the test is further reduced by using the CADIS variance reduction technique to speedup the MCNP Monte Carlo simulations. This section will describe the PENTRAN and MCNP models used, the DRF method for the test problem, and the implementation of CADIS.

3.1. MCNP and PENTRAN Modeling

The test problem is best understood using the MCNP model. Figure 1 shows a labeled axial view of the MCNP model. The iron dosimeter shown is positioned radially behind the neutron pad and axially aligned with the top of the reactor core. The iron dosimeter is a cylinder with a radius of 2 cm and a height of 22.031 cm.

Figure 1. Axial Geometry of MCNP Model.

Only one portion of one fuel rod is used as a source for this test. Figure 2 shows the selected fuel rod in its fuel assembly. This rod is selected since it lies close to the dosimeter which means its contribution to the dosimeter response is high. Figure 3 is the PENTRAN model used for this test problem. This

model comprises 16 coarse meshes, 75,000 fine meshes, utilization of the ADS differencing technique, S_{12} angular quadrature, and the first 21 groups of the 47-group BIGLE-B7 multigroup cross-section library.

Figure 2. Limited Test Region

Figure 3. PENTRAN Corss-Section Geometry

The geometric portion of the LTR is shown in Figure 2 and consists of the top quarter (91.44 cm) of the selected fuel rod. A combination of the geometric LTR and the top 7 energy groups shown in Table I form the complete LTR. The source used in this problem is a uniform source across space with the χ_g

distribution given in Table I. An integration of the U^{235} Watt Spectrum is used to calculate the χ_g .

Table I. Energy Limited Test Region for Test Problem

Energy Group Number	Maximum Energy (MeV)	χ_g	Iron Group-wise σ_d
1	17.33	7.10×10^{-4}	0.357
2	14.19	3.08×10^{-3}	0.494
3	12.21	1.86×10^{-2}	0.539
4	10.00	4.41×10^{-2}	0.532
5	8.607	9.98×10^{-2}	0.517
6	7.408	2.86×10^{-1}	0.497
7	6.0657	5.48×10^{-1}	0.439

3.2. DRF Calculations

The DRF method subdivides the source phase-space, the LTR in this case, into sub-regions, called source regions, using both spatial and energy divisions. This test problem has 28 total source regions since the LTR is divided into 4 axial intervals, shown in Figure 2, with 7 energy groups for each interval. The dosimetry response R_i is given by

$$R_i = \sum_{j=1}^I \alpha_{i,j} S_j \quad (1)$$

$\alpha_{i,j}$ is the DRF coefficient for source region "j" and dosimeter "i", and S_j is the source from source region "j".

DRF coefficients are calculated through MCNP fixed-source calculations. A single DRF coefficient is calculated by selecting one source region, performing a fixed-source calculation with the source region as the source, tallying the neutron flux at the dosimeter, and multiplying the tallied neutron flux by the σ_d of the iron dosimeter given in Table I. Repeating the calculation process for each source region produces a complete set of DRF coefficients that can be used in Equation (1). The test is conducted for two other fuel rods whose locations are shown in Figure 4.

3.3. Reference Calculation

Results from the DRF method are compared to a reference MCNP Monte Carlo calculation using CADIS that solves the dosimeter response. The reference calculation involves performing a fixed-source calculation using the entire LTR as the source, tallying the neutron flux at the dosimeter, and multiplying the flux with the σ_d of the iron dosimeter. The reference calculation uses the same model as the DRF method shown in Figure 2.

3.4. CADIS Implementation

Tallying flux at the dosimeter takes too long when using Monte Carlo Calculations without variance reduction, so CADIS is implemented for both the DRF calculation and the reference calculation to reduce calculation time. CADIS utilizes an estimated importance function to inform both transport biasing and source biasing in a Monte Carlo calculation [2].

Figure 4. PENTRAN Corss-Section Geometry

3.4.1. Importance Calculations

PENTRAN is used to calculate an approximate importance function. The importance calculation uses the σ_d of the iron dosimeter as the importance source. Figure 3 shows the PENTRAN fine mesh distribution in the X and Y directions. The approximate importance is calculated for 3,525,000 phase-space cells which arises from the model discretization of 50 fine meshes in the X direction, 50 fine meshes in the Y direction, 30 fine meshes in the Z direction, and 47 energy groups. The first 21 groups (0.7 MeV - 17.3 MeV) of the BUGLE-B7 cross-section library are considered to determine 21-group importance function [9].

An approximate dosimeter response value is calculated from the approximate importance using Equation (2).

$$R_{approx} = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{g=1}^G \chi_g V_j \phi_{j,g}^* q_{j,g} \quad (2)$$

Where R_{approx} is the approximate dosimeter response, $\phi_{j,g}^*$ is the importance value at fine mesh i and energy group g, and V_j is the volume of fine mesh j. The source distribution, $q_{i,g}$, is assumed to be uniform across each fine mesh in the fuel region and zero everywhere else for this test.

3.4.2. Weight Window Generation

The approximate dosimeter response and importance is used to determine the weight window parameters for transport biasing. The weight window lower boundary is found using Equation (3)

$$wwl_{j,g} = \frac{2R_{approx}}{\phi_{j,g}^* (c + 1)} \quad (3)$$

Where $wl_{j,g}$ is the lower bound of the weight window for fine mesh "j" and energy group "g", and c is the ratio between the higher and lower weight window boundaries. In this case c is 5 as recommended in pages 551-552 of [7].

The weight window lower boundaries are used as input in the MCNP wwinp file. This file enables MCNP to use the CADIS variance reduction technique.

3.4.3. Source Biasing

The CADIS method uses the approximate importance and dosimetry response to perform source biasing for further reduction of computation time. The biased source is calculated using Equation (4).

$$q_{j,g}^* = \frac{\phi_{j,g}^* q_{j,g}}{R_{approx}} \quad (4)$$

Where $q_{j,g}^*$ is the biased source of fine mesh "j" and energy group "g". Using the biased source requires adjusting the weight of the source particles to not bias the results as show in Equation (5).

$$w = \frac{q_{j,g}}{q_{j,g}^*} = \frac{R_{approx}}{\phi_{j,g}^*} \quad (5)$$

Where w is the source weight of a biased source particle.

The weight of the biased source particle is equal to the central weight of the weight window as shown in Equation (6).

$$w w c_{j,g} = \frac{(1+c) w l_{j,g}}{2} = \frac{(1+c)}{2} \frac{2 R_{approx}}{\phi_{j,g}^* (c+1)} = \frac{R_{approx}}{\phi_{j,g}^*} \quad (6)$$

Where $w w c_{j,g}$ is the center weight of the weight window at fine mesh "j" and energy group "g".

Note that in this study does not use source biasing because of the source region's small volume.

4. RESULTS

A comparison of the calculated dosimeter response from the DRF method and the reference MCNP calculation are presented in Table II, Table III, and Table IV. All three fuel rods shown that the DRF method is within 5% relative difference of the reference. The test for fuel rods 2 and 3 are to improve confidence in the comparison.

Table II. Results and Comparison

Method	Dosimeter Response ($\frac{tally}{source}$)	Statistical Error	Starting Weight
DRF Method	0.17374		5.13E+05
Reference Calculation	0.16826	0.0062	5.13E+05
Relative Difference (%)	3.26		

These results suggest that there is enough agreement between the two methods of determining dosimeter response that the DRF method can be applied to the entire model.

5. FUTURE WORK

The limited scope of this test means it can only act as a staging point for future work. The calculation of approximate dosimetry response in Equation (2) does not account for χ_g which will produce slightly

Table III. Results for LTR 2

Method	Dosimeter Response ($\frac{\text{tally}}{\text{source}}$)	Statistical Error	Starting Weight
DRF Method	0.10538		3.19E+05
Reference Calculation	0.11021	0.0273	3.19E+05
Relative Difference (%)	4.39		

Table IV. Results for LTR 3

Method	Dosimeter Response ($\frac{\text{tally}}{\text{source}}$)	Statistical Error	Starting Weight
DRF Method	0.07251		3.22E+06
Reference Calculation	0.07367	0.0336	3.22E+06
Relative Difference (%)	1.57		

incorrect dosimeter response values. The next step for developing the DRF method is to estimate the field of view (FOV) accurately through determination of DRF coefficients in different assemblies with the highest contribution to the dosimeter of interest.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a preliminary test to evaluate the accuracy of using the DRF method to compute a dosimeter response in the Watts Bar Unit 1 reactor. The DRF results are compared against a reference MCNP Monte Carlo calculation, and good agreement is observed between the two methods.

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